

How PHP engine builds AST

Anton Sukhachev

Abstract: This article explains how the PHP engine builds an Abstract Syntax Tree (AST) from PHP code. It describes how the lexer and parser work together inside the Zend Engine. The lexer is generated with re2c, and the parser is created with Bison using grammar rules written in BNF. The post shows how tokens are recognized, how they are converted into AST nodes, and how the functions `zendlex`, `zendparse`, and `zend_compile_string_to_ast` are connected. It also includes examples of getting and printing the real PHP AST through FFI. The article helps developers understand how PHP translates code into an internal structure before execution.

Keywords: PHP, PHP engine, Zend Engine, AST, parsing pipeline, compiler internals

First let's look at the PHP codeflow:

Prior to version 7, PHP generated OPcodes right inside the parser. PHP 7 introduced a new code abstraction - [AST](#).

Now we can separate parsing and compilation.

In this post I want to talk about the Lexer + Parser part.

PHP uses re2c to create a lexer and Bison to create a parser. If you don't know about these tools, I recommend reading this [post](#).

Let's start with the lexer.

The main function of the lexer is to parse the code into tokens.

The PHP 8 tokenizer module provides us with the [PhpToken](#) class to parse code into tokens. This is very similar to PHP's internal lexer.

Let's write `lexer.php` and use it to parse the `test.php` file.

`lexer.php`

```
<?php

$code = file_get_contents($argv[1]);

$tokens = PhpToken::tokenize($code);

foreach ($tokens as $token) {
    echo $token->getTokenName() . " ";
}
```

`test.php`

```
<?php

$a = 1;

echo $a;
```

lexer.php output:

```
php lexer.php test.php
T_OPEN_TAG
T_WHITESPACE
T_VARIABLE T_WHITESPACE = T_WHITESPACE T_LNUMBER ;
T_WHITESPACE
T_ECHO T_WHITESPACE T_VARIABLE ;
```

I put the contents of test.php and the output of lexer.php in the same place for a better comparison:

```
<?php      |   T_OPEN_TAG
           |   T_WHITESPACE
$a = 1;    |   T_VARIABLE T_WHITESPACE = T_WHITESPACE T_LNUMBER ;
           |   T_WHITESPACE
echo $a;   |   T_ECHO T_WHITESPACE T_VARIABLE ;
```

How does the PHP lexer parse code into tokens?

re2c helps with this.

[re2c](#) is an open-source lexer generator. It uses regular expressions to recognize tokens.

The PHP lexer code is in [zend_language_scanner.l](#)

The main function that recognizes the code and returns the token is `lex_scan`:

[zend_language_scanner.l](#)

```
int ZEND_FASTCALL lex_scan(zval *zendlval, zend_parser_stack_elem *elem)
{
    ...

    /*!re2c
re2c:yyfill:check = 0;
LNUM    [0-9]+(_[0-9]+)*
DNUM    ({LNUM}?"."{LNUM})|({LNUM}"". "{LNUM}?)
EXPONENT_DNUM  (({LNUM}|{DNUM})[eE][+-]?{LNUM})
HNUM    "0x"[0-9a-fA-F]+(_[0-9a-fA-F]+)*
BNUM    "0b"[01]+(_[01]+)*
ONUM    "0o"[0-7]+(_[0-7]+)*

    ...

<ST_IN_SCRIPTING>"exit" {
    RETURN_TOKEN_WITH_IDENT(T_EXIT);
}

<ST_IN_SCRIPTING>"const" {
    RETURN_TOKEN_WITH_IDENT(T_CONST);
}
```

```

<ST_IN_SCRIPTING>"return" {
    RETURN_TOKEN_WITH_IDENT(T_RETURN);
}

...

*/

```

After the lexer we have tokens, but we need a parser to build AST.
Bison can help us with this.

[Bison](#) is an open-source context-free parser generator.
It can generate a parser from [BNF](#).

Example of Bison BNF:

```

line:
    %empty
|   expr { printf("%d", $1); }
;

expr:
    TOK_NUMBER    { $$ = $1; }
|   expr '+' expr { $$ = $1 + $3; }
|   expr '-' expr { $$ = $1 - $3; }
;

```

The parser code is in [zend_language_parser.y](#)

For example, this part parses PHP attributes ([#\[Attribute\]](#))
[zend_language_parser.y](#)

```

attribute_decl:
    class_name
        { $$ = zend_ast_create(ZEND_AST_ATTRIBUTE, $1, NULL); }
|   class_name argument_list
        { $$ = zend_ast_create(ZEND_AST_ATTRIBUTE, $1, $2); }
;

```

When the parser finds a PHP attribute, it calls `zend_ast_create` function.
[zend_ast.c](#)

```

ZEND_API zend_ast *zend_ast_create(zend_ast_kind kind, ...)

```

`zend_ast_create` is one of several functions that help create an AST node.

PHP represents the AST node as a `_zend_ast` structure for simple nodes, and several more complex structures for other nodes.

[zend_ast.h](#)

```
struct _zend_ast {
    zend_ast_kind kind; /* Type of the node (ZEND_AST_* enum constant) */
    zend_ast_attr attr; /* Additional attribute, use depending on node
type */
    uint32_t lineno; /* Line number */
    zend_ast *child[1]; /* Array of children (using struct hack) */
};
```

The main parser function is `yyparse`. You don't need to write it - `Bison` will generate it itself; Each time `yyparse` needs to get the next token, it calls the `yylex` lexer function. We already have the lexer function `lex_scan`.

How do parser and lexer work together?

`Bison` has parameter `api.prefix`:

[zend_language_parser.y](#)

```
%define api.prefix {zend}
```

This means that all function prefixes will be `zend` instead of `yy`:

`yyparse` -> `zendparse`

`yylex` -> `zendlex`

We have the `zendlex` function in

[zend_compile.c](#)

```
int ZEND_FASTCALL zendlex(zend_parser_stack_elem *elem)
```

it calls the already known `lex_scan` function from [zend_language_scanner.l](#)

And `zendparse` is called in the function `zend_compile_string_to_ast`

[zend_language_scanner.l](#)

```
ZEND_API zend_ast *zend_compile_string_to_ast(zend_string *code,
zend_arena **ast_arena, zend_string *filename)
```

In the final, we have a chain of calls:

```
zend_compile_string_to_ast() -> zendparse() -> zendlex() -> lex_scan()
```

Now we can call the `zend_compile_string_to_ast` function and get the real PHP AST. I wrote a `get_ast` function to get the AST from `zend_compile_string_to_ast`, parse it and store it in a simple structure `_node_ast` so we can easily export it to PHP using [FFI](#).
[mrsuh/ast.c](#)

```
node_ast *get_ast(char *input)
```

[mrsuh/ast.h](#)

```
struct _node_ast {
    const char *kind;
    const char *attr;
    const char *value;
    int lineno;
    int children;
    node_ast *child[100];
};
```

After compilation, I included it in PHP

[mrsuh/Parser.php](#)

```
<?php

self::$libc = \FFI::cdef(
"
typedef struct _node_ast node_ast;

struct _node_ast {
    const char *kind;
    const char *attr;
    const char *value;
    int lineno;
    int children;
    node_ast *child[100];
};

node_ast *get_ast(char *input);
",
__DIR__ . "ast_linux.so");
```

and translated the C structure into a PHP Node class.

[mrsuh/Node.php](#)

```
<?php

namespace Mrsuh\PhpAst;

final class Node
{
    public string $kind    = "";
    public string $value  = "";
    public int    $lineno = 0;
    /** @var Node[] */
    public array $children = [];
}
```

Let's parse some code into AST:

[mrsuh/parse.php](#)

```
<?php

require __DIR__ . '/vendor/autoload.php';

use Mrsuh\PhpAst\Parser;
use Mrsuh\PhpAst\Printer;

$code = <<<'CODE'
<?php

namespace App;

class Test
{
    public function test($foo)
    {
        var_dump($foo);
    }
}
CODE;

$node = Parser::parse($code);
Printer::print($node);
```

mrsuh/parse.php output:

```
php parse.php
[001] ZEND_AST_STMT_LIST
[003]   ZEND_AST_NAMESPACE
[003]     ZEND_AST_ZVAL "App"
[005]   ZEND_AST_CLASS "Test"
[006]     ZEND_AST_STMT_LIST
[007]       ZEND_AST_METHOD "test"
[007]         ZEND_AST_PARAM_LIST
[007]           ZEND_AST_PARAM
[007]             ZEND_AST_ZVAL "foo"
[008]       ZEND_AST_STMT_LIST
[009]         ZEND_AST_CALL
[009]           ZEND_AST_ZVAL "var_dump"
[009]             ZEND_AST_ARG_LIST
[009]               ZEND_AST_VAR
[009]                 ZEND_AST_ZVAL "foo"
```

The complete parser code is [here](#).

Nikita Popov already has a php-ast parser that uses `zend_compile_string_to_ast` function and a php-parser that uses the PHP tokenizer module as a lexer and a PHP version of YACC as a parser generator.

Below I have shown the outputs of three libraries for this code:

test.php

```
<?php
$a = 1;

echo $a;
```

[mrsuh/php-ast](#)

```
[001] ZEND_AST_STMT_LIST
[003]   ZEND_AST_ASSIGN
[003]     ZEND_AST_VAR
[003]       ZEND_AST_ZVAL "a"
[003]     ZEND_AST_ZVAL "1"
[005]   ZEND_AST_STMT_LIST
[005]     ZEND_AST_ECHO
[005]       ZEND_AST_VAR
[005]         ZEND_AST_ZVAL "a"
```

[nikic/php-ast](#)

```
AST_STMT_LIST
  0: AST_ASSIGN
    var: AST_VAR
      name: "a"
    expr: 1
  1: AST_ECHO
    expr: AST_VAR
      name: "a"
```

[nikic/PHP-Parser](#)

```
array(
  0: Stmt_Expression(
    expr: Expr_Assign(
      var: Expr_Variable(
        name: a
      )
      expr: Scalar_LNumber(
        value: 1
      )
    )
  )
  1: Stmt_Echo(
    exprs: array(
      0: Expr_Variable(
        name: a
      )
    )
  )
)
```

As for me, it looks very similar.

There are additional resources if you want to know more:

- <https://www.codeproject.com/Articles/1035799/Generating-a-High-Speed-Parser-Part-re-c>
- <https://www.cs.montana.edu/techreports/1011/Wickland.pdf>
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Z7uLTS55Ifo>